

Impact of ChatGPT Acceptance on Critical Thinking Disposition among College Students in Butuan City: A Basis for Module Development

Diana Shane M. Ranara, Rpm

Master's Degree Student, School of Counseling and Psychology, San Pedro College, Philippines

Henry M. Yap, PhD, RGC

Dean, School of Counseling and Psychology, San Pedro College, Philippines

Abstract

The rapid integration of generative AI, such as ChatGPT, in higher education has raised concerns about its role in shaping college students' thinking processes. This study investigates whether ChatGPT Acceptance translates into stronger Critical Thinking Disposition among college students in Butuan City and examines which dimensions of ChatGPT Acceptance contribute to this outcome. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, data were collected from 359 students selected through stratified random sampling across three higher education institutions. Measures included ChatGPT Acceptance—perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, intrinsic motivation, and behavioral intention, and Critical Thinking Dispositions. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Spearman's rho, and multiple linear regression. Findings revealed high levels of both ChatGPT Acceptance ($M = 4.12$) and Critical Thinking Disposition ($M = 3.66$). However, the correlation analysis indicated a very weak, non-significant relationship between the two constructs ($\rho \approx .067$), suggesting that widespread ChatGPT Acceptance does not automatically translate into critical thinking. Notably, regression results demonstrated that only perceived ease of use significantly predicted Critical Thinking Disposition ($B = 0.177$, $p < .001$), accounting for 4.2% of the variance, while perceived usefulness, intrinsic motivation, and behavioral intention were not significant predictors. These findings challenge the idea that acceptance alone does not foster growth in critical thinking disposition. Instead, suggest reconceptualizing AI integration as a pedagogically mediated process. In response, this study advances a structured instructional intervention, ChatGPT-Assisted Training for Critical Thinking Disposition, designed to transform passive ChatGPT use into guided, cognitively engaging learning experiences.

Keywords: *ChatGPT Acceptance, Critical Thinking Disposition, Perceive Ease of Use, AI Literacy.*

Suggested citation: Ranara, D.S.M., & Yap, H.M. (2026). Impact of ChatGPT Acceptance on Critical Thinking Disposition among College Students in Butuan City: A Basis for Module Development. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 4(3), 31-40. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2026.4(3).03

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

The rapid integration of artificial intelligence in higher education has transformed how college students engage with learning, raising critical questions about its influence on thinking processes (Chai et al., 2020). Among these AI tools, ChatGPT has become widely adopted due to its accessibility and capacity to generate human-like responses that support academic tasks such as idea generation, drafting, and feedback (Sušnjak, 2022). While these offers enhance efficiency, growing concerns suggest that uncritical reliance on AI may promote surface-level learning, reduce intellectual effort, and weaken students' critical thinking disposition. This tension positions ChatGPT not merely as a tool for productivity, but as a factor that may reshape college students who are technologically proficient but lack the critical thinking disposition necessary for sound decision-making, ethical judgment, and effective problem-solving in both academic and real-world contexts.

Critical thinking disposition, as conceptualized by Facione (1990), refers to the consistent internal motivation to engage in reflective, analytical, and evidence-based thinking. Unlike cognitive skills alone, disposition determines whether individuals choose to apply critical thinking in problem-solving contexts (Facione et al., 1995; Facione, 2015). Students with strong dispositions are more likely to evaluate evidence, consider alternative perspectives, and regulate their reasoning processes, leading to more effective decision-making (Jaswal & Behera, 2023). In this, the impact of ChatGPT depends not only on its functionality but also on the user's disposition toward critical engagement.

The existing literature presents conflicting perspectives on the role of ChatGPT acceptance in shaping critical thinking dispositions. Some studies highlight its potential to scaffold learning, enhance cognitive engagement, and support analytical reasoning when used deliberately (Huang et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2023). Others caution that excessive reliance may undermine higher-order thinking, academic integrity, and independent reasoning (Farrokhnia et al., 2023; Wu, 2024). Empirical data further reflect this divergence, with widespread student usage reported globally (Tan, 2023; Statista, 2025) alongside concerns about dependency and cognitive offloading (Kung et al., 2023). These contradictions suggest that ChatGPT's effects are not uniform but contingent on how students engage with the technology.

Despite the growing body of research, a critical gap remains. Most studies have focused on outcomes such as performance, motivation, and productivity, often neglecting dispositional constructs, particularly critical thinking disposition, and in non-Western contexts. In the Philippines, the increasing use of artificial intelligence in higher education aligns with national efforts to promote digital transformation and technology-enhanced learning. This study extends existing literature by developing a structured instructional intervention, ChatGPT-Assisted Training for Critical Thinking Disposition, designed to transform passive AI use into guided, cognitively engaging learning experiences. By empirically examining the link between ChatGPT Acceptance and Critical Thinking Disposition, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of AI integration in education—one that recognizes that technological

adoption alone is insufficient without pedagogical structures that cultivate reflective and critical engagement.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational design to examine the relationship between ChatGPT acceptance and critical thinking disposition. The study was conducted in Butuan City, Agusan del Norte, Philippines, involving three higher education institutions (University A, University B, and Institution C). The target population consisted of 21,040 college students enrolled during the 2024–2025 academic year. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized to ensure proportional representation across institutions and year levels. A sample size of 378 respondents was determined using the Raosoft calculator (95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, 50% response distribution). After data screening, 21 outliers were removed, resulting in a final sample of 359 respondents. Outlier removal improved the distributional assumptions, including normality of residuals, homoscedasticity, and absence of multicollinearity, without inflating statistical relationships.

ChatGPT Acceptance was measured using the Extension of Technology Acceptance Model (ETAM) questionnaire developed by Lai, Cheung, and Chan (2023), consisting of 16 items across four constructs: perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, intrinsic motivation, and behavioral intention. The instrument demonstrated good reliability ($\alpha = 0.860$; subscales ranged from 0.724 to 0.801). While Critical Thinking Disposition was measured using a 24-item questionnaire adapted from Boonsathirakul and Kerdsomboon (2021), grounded in the California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (Facione, 1990). The overall reliability was acceptable ($\alpha = 0.787$), although some subscales showed lower internal consistency, reflecting variability in dispositional constructs. Both instruments used a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree), with corresponding interpretive levels (Very Low to Very High).

In the data analysis, descriptive statistics were used to determine the levels of ChatGPT Acceptance and Critical Thinking Disposition. Spearman's rho correlation was employed to examine the relationship between variables. Moreover, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine which dimensions of ChatGPT Acceptance significantly predicted Critical Thinking Disposition. Assumptions of regression, including normality of residuals, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity, were assessed and met after data cleaning.

Results

The level of ChatGPT Acceptance among college students is presented in Table 1. The overall mean score was 4.12 (SD = 0.78), indicating a High level of acceptance. Among the dimensions, perceived ease of use obtained the highest mean (M = 4.48, SD = 0.68), while behavioral intention had the lowest mean (M = 3.79, SD = 0.84). All dimensions demonstrated relatively low coefficients of variation, indicating consistent responses across participants.

Table 1. Level of ChatGPT Acceptance of College Students

ChatGPT Acceptance	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variation	Verbal Interpretation
Perceive Ease of Use	4.48	0.68	15.16%	Very High

Perceive Usefulness	4.17	0.80	19.26%	High
Intrinsic Motivation	4.02	0.79	19.70%	High
Behavioral Intention	3.79	0.84	22.19%	High
Overall	4.12	0.78	18.95%	High

The level of Critical Thinking Disposition is presented in Table 2. The overall mean score was 3.66 (SD = 0.85), corresponding to a High level. Among the dimensions, inquisitiveness (M = 4.30, SD = 0.69) and analyticity (M = 4.23, SD = 0.68) were rated Very High, while cognitive maturity (M = 2.62, SD = 1.10) was rated Moderate and showed the highest variability.

Table 2. Level of Critical Thinking Disposition of College Students

Critical Thinking Disposition	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variation	Verbal Interpretation
Inquisitiveness	4.30	0.69	16.02%	Very High
Analyticity	4.23	0.68	16.12%	Very High
Open-mindedness	3.93	0.86	22.32%	High
Systematicity	3.61	0.85	23.57%	High
Self-confidence	3.52	0.78	22.16%	High
Truth-seeking	3.44	0.98	28.55%	High
Cognitive Maturity	2.62	1.10	41.91%	Moderate
Overall	3.66	0.85	23.16%	High

The relationship between ChatGPT Acceptance and Critical Thinking Disposition is presented in Table 3. Spearman's rho analysis yielded a correlation coefficient of $\rho = .067$, indicating a very weak positive relationship. The result was not statistically significant ($p = .207$), leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 3. Relationship Between ChatGPT Acceptance and Critical Thinking Disposition

Variables	Spearman's rho value	Strength	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
ChatGPT Acceptance and Critical Thinking Dispositio	.067	Very weak positive relationship	.207	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The influence of ChatGPT Acceptance dimensions on Critical Thinking Disposition is presented in Table 4. Multiple linear regression analysis showed that the overall model was statistically significant, $F(4, 354) = 3.89$, $p = .004$, with $R^2 = .042$ and Adjusted $R^2 = .031$, indicating that the model explained 4.2% of the variance in Critical Thinking Disposition. Among the predictors, perceived ease of use was the only variable that showed a statistically significant effect ($B = 0.177$, $p < .001$). The variables perceived usefulness ($p = .972$), intrinsic motivation ($p = .842$), and behavioral intention ($p = .075$) were not statistically significant.

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of ChatGPT Acceptance Dimensions

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	3.182	0.203	15.694	.000	
Perceive ease of use	0.177	0.049	3.607	.000	Significant

Perceive usefulness	-0.002	0.049	-0.035	.972	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	0.009	0.047	0.199	.842	Not Significant
Behavioral Intention	-0.073	0.041	-1.788	.075	Not Significant

Discussion

The results indicate that college students have a Very High level of perceived ease of use regarding ChatGPT Acceptance. This reflects students' belief that a technology requires little effort to operate, and the results show that college students view ChatGPT as very easy and comfortable to use. They find its interface intuitive, its functions easy to navigate, and its features easy to understand, allowing them to focus on their academic tasks rather than spend time figuring out how the tool works. This shared positive perception suggests that usability significantly contributes to their overall ChatGPT acceptance. This finding is consistent with the Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model by Lai, Cheung, and Chan (2023), which suggests that perceived ease of use strongly predicts technology adoption (Davis, 1989). This aligns with prior studies indicating that user-friendly technologies enhance engagement and reduce extraneous cognitive load (Yilmaz et al., 2023). However, the findings suggest that interface aesthetics and conversational design may also influence perceived ease of use, consistent with the aesthetic–usability effect (Admin & Admin, 2025; Altaboli & Lin, 2011). Thus, acceptance may reflect not only functional usability but also perceived usability shaped by psychological and affective factors.

The findings on Critical Thinking Disposition suggest that while college students demonstrated strong inquisitiveness and analyticity, cognitive maturity emerged as the weakest and most variable dimension. This is consistent with Facione's (1990) conceptualization of critical thinking dispositions; inquisitiveness serves as the intellectual curiosity that drives individuals toward continuous learning and reflective thinking (Wade & Kidd, 2019; Boyer et al., 2013), while dispositions such as truth-seeking and cognitive maturity are more developmentally complex and less stable (Gilbert et al., 2025; Gómez et al., 2025; Ansori et al., 2018). Empirical studies suggest that cognitive maturity is closely linked to metacognitive awareness and tolerance for ambiguity, which develop through guided reflection and exposure to complex problem-solving tasks (Toplak, 2021; Karakuş, 2024; Gómez et al., 2025). The results of the critical thinking disposition have significant implications for the current post-pandemic educational landscape, where blended and online learning have increased students' exposure to vast amounts of unfiltered information. From a developmental perspective, this aligns with research on emerging adulthood, where reflective judgment and executive functioning continue to evolve (Gilbert et al., 2025). Instructionally, educators can design AI literacy modules and structured critical thinking interventions that challenge college students to evaluate ChatGPT's output, detect biases, and compare AI-generated information with credible sources (Andreucci-Annunziata et al., 2023).

Despite these high levels of ChatGPT Acceptance, the results revealed a very weak, non-significant relationship between ChatGPT Acceptance and Critical Thinking Disposition. Recent research suggests that students use ChatGPT for convenience or time-saving rather than to deepen reflective thinking, limiting its impact on the development of critical thinking traits (Vázquez-Cano et al., 2023; Cavazos et al., 2024; Chow, 2025). Students generally perceive ChatGPT as a helpful academic tool, primarily for tasks such as summarizing, generating outlines, and correcting grammar; however, this usage tends to be surface-level, focusing on efficiency rather than critical

engagement (Chan & Hu, 2023). Facione (1990) explained that Critical Thinking Disposition is a set of enduring attitudes rather than a byproduct of tool use. The present findings suggest that students' interaction with ChatGPT remains largely procedural rather than metacognitive, thereby limiting its impact on dispositional development.

On the other hand, the regression analysis reveals that among the four dimensions of ChatGPT Acceptance, only perceived ease of use significantly influences Critical Thinking Disposition, whereas perceived usefulness, intrinsic motivation, and behavioral intention do not. This finding can be interpreted through Cognitive Load Theory, which posits that reducing extraneous cognitive load allows learners to allocate more cognitive resources to higher-order processes such as analysis and evaluation (Becker et al. (2025). Supporting this, research on AI-supported learning environments suggests that intuitive interfaces facilitate deeper engagement when learners are not burdened by operational complexity (Kim et al., 2020; Zou & Huang, 2023). However, the relatively small variance explained indicates that ease of use functions primarily as an enabling condition rather than a sufficient driver of critical thinking development. This explains that deeper cognitive outcomes depend on factors beyond usability, including instructional design and metacognitive engagement.

The findings highlight the importance of structured pedagogical approaches that guide college students in using ChatGPT as a tool for inquiry, evaluation, and reflection rather than passive consumption. Evidence suggests that ChatGPT use enhances critical thinking when paired with structured questioning, argument evaluation, and guided dialogue (Guo & Lee, 2023; Lee et al., 2024). These foster a psychologically safe space where students can engage with ChatGPT critically, without becoming dependent on it for cognitive shortcuts. In response, a 9-week module, CHAT-CTD: ChatGPT-Assisted Training for Critical Thinking Disposition, was developed using Bybee et al.'s (2006) 5E Instructional Model to scaffold learning from engagement to reflective evaluation. The module integrates evidence-based strategies emphasizing AI literacy, metacognition, and structured inquiry (Ngo & Hastie, 2024; Guo & Lee, 2023; Lee et al., 2024), incorporating guided questioning, argument evaluation, and reflective tasks. Designed for both instructional and support contexts, it provides a research-based, replicable framework that transforms ChatGPT use from a convenience-driven tool into a structured process for developing critical thinking disposition in ChatGPT-integrated learning environments.

Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence that widespread ChatGPT Acceptance among college students does not inherently translate into the development of Critical Thinking Disposition. While students demonstrate high levels of acceptance—driven by perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, intrinsic motivation, and behavioral intention these do not correspond to meaningful reflective judgment, evaluative reasoning, or metacognitive engagement.

The results contribute to the theoretical integration of the Extended Technology Acceptance Model and Critical Thinking Disposition frameworks by demonstrating their conceptual limits when applied independently. While acceptance models effectively explain why students adopt AI technologies such as ChatGPT, they do not account for the depth of cognitive engagement required for dispositional change. The identification of perceived ease of use as the only significant predictor further refines

this relationship, suggesting that usability functions as an enabling condition that reduces cognitive load but does not, in itself, sustain critical thinking. This suggests that perceived ease of use indicates that when ChatGPT is intuitive and effortless to navigate, students can allocate cognitive resources more freely for reasoning and problem-solving, rather than being a transformative driver of cognitive development.

From a broader perspective, the findings have implications for educational psychology, instructional design, and AI-integrated learning environments. Suggest that the role of artificial intelligence in education must be reframed, not as a tool that directly enhances thinking, but as a mediating context that can either support or constrain cognitive engagement depending on how it is used. In this study, students exhibited strong inquisitiveness and analyticity, yet lower and more variable cognitive maturity, indicating that while learners are capable of engaging with information, they require structured opportunities to develop reflective judgment and tolerance for ambiguity. This highlights a developmental and pedagogical gap that cannot be addressed solely through exposure to technology.

These findings proposed an intentional, scaffolded integration of ChatGPT within instructional and support systems. The CHAT-CTD: ChatGPT-Assisted Training for Critical Thinking Disposition module represents a research-based response demonstrating how ChatGPT can be repositioned from a convenience-oriented tool into a structured platform for inquiry, evaluation, and metacognitive reflection. This has broader relevance for curriculum development, faculty training, and institutional policy, particularly in the design of AI literacy initiatives that prioritize not only technical proficiency but also critical and ethical engagement.

The study also raises important questions for future research. Given the correlational nature of the design, causal relationships remain undetermined, and the model's relatively low explanatory power suggests the presence of unexamined factors. Future research should investigate mediating and moderating variables, such as metacognitive awareness, instructional practices, and learning environments, to explain better how ChatGPT acceptance and use interact with cognitive development. Longitudinal and experimental studies are particularly needed to examine whether sustained, guided engagement with ChatGPT can produce measurable changes in critical thinking disposition over time. Additionally, comparative studies across different AI platforms may reveal how variations in system design influence patterns of cognitive engagement.

Lastly, as ChatGPT and other AI platforms become increasingly embedded in academic contexts, the central challenge is not whether students will use these technologies, but whether such use is structured in ways that promote reflective, analytical, and intellectually responsible thinking. By reframing AI as a cognitive scaffold rather than a cognitive substitute, this research contributes to a more nuanced and sustainable model of human–AI learning in higher education.

References

- Admin, & Admin. (2025, May 3). How a rounded aesthetic translates beauty to function and prosociality: The Persuasive Effects of Warmth - JUX. *JUX - The Journal of User Experience*. <https://uxpajournal.org/rounded-aesthetic-beauty-warmth/>
- Altaboli, A., & Lin, Y. (2011). Investigating effects of screen layout elements on interface and screen design aesthetics. *Advances in Human-Computer Interaction, 2011*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/659758>

Andreucci-Annunziata, P., Riedemann, A., Cortés, S., Mellado, A., Del Río, M. T., & Vega-Muñoz, A. (2023). Conceptualizations and instructional strategies on critical thinking in higher education: A systematic review of systematic reviews. *Frontiers in Education*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1141686>

Ansori, A. Z., Ibrahim, M., & Widodo, W. (2018). Theoretical study of the a truth-seeking learning model: The learning model to improve students critical thinking disposition. *Atlantis Press*, 2352–5398. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icomse-17.2018.22>

Becker, E., Wünsche, J., Veith, J. M., Schrader, J., & Bitzenbauer, P. (2025, August 8). From Cognitive relief to Affective Engagement: An empirical comparison of AI chatbots and instructional scaffolding in physics education. *arXiv.org*. https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.06254?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Boonsathirakul, J., & Kerdsomboon, C. (2021). The investigation of critical thinking disposition among Kasetsart University students. *Higher Education Studies*, 11(2), 224. <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v11n2p224>

Boyer, S. L., Edmondson, D. R., Artis, A. B., & Fleming, D. (2013). Self-directed learning: A tool for lifelong learning. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 36(1), 20–32. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0273475313494010>

Bybee, Rodger & Taylor, Joseph & Gardner, April & Scotter, Pamela & Carlson, Janet & Westbrook, Anne & Landes, Nancy. (2006). The BSCS 5E Instructional Model: Origins, Effectiveness, and Applications. BSCS

Cavazos, J. T., Hauck, K. A., Baskin, H. M., & Bain, C. M. (2024). ChatGPT goes to college: Exploring student perspectives on artificial intelligence in the classroom. *Teaching of Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00986283241268829>

Chai, C.S., Lin, P. Y., Jong, M.S., Dai, Y., Chiu, T.K.F., and Huang, B. (2020). Factors influencing students' behavioral intention to continue artificial intelligence Learning. *International Symposium on Educational Technology (ISET), Bangkok, Thailand, 2020*, pp. 147-150, DOI:[10.1109/ISET49818.2020.00040](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISET49818.2020.00040)

Chan, C. K. Y., & Hu, W. (2023). Students' voices on generative AI: perceptions, benefits, and challenges in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00411-8>

Chow, A. R. (2025, November 13). ChatGPT may be eroding critical thinking skills, according to a new MIT study. *TIME*. https://time.com/7295195/ai-chatgpt-google-learning-school/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>

Facione, P. (2015). Critical thinking: what it is and why it counts. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/251303244_Critical_Thinking_What_It_Is_and_Why_It_Counts

Facione, P. A. (1990). *Critical Thinking: A Statement of Expert Consensus for Purposes of Educational Assessment and Instruction*. The Delphi Report. Millbrae, CA: The California Academic Press.

Facione, P., Sanchez, C., Facione, N., & Gainen, J. (1995). The Disposition Towards Critical Thinking. *The Journal of General Education*, Vol. 44, No. 1 (1995), pp. 1-25. Retrieved from

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/241897896> The Disposition Toward Critical Thinking 1

Farrokhnia, M., Banihashem, S. K., Noroozi, O., & Wals, A. (2023). A SWOT analysis of ChatGPT: Implications for educational practice and research. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2023.2195846>

Gilbert, L. M., Williams, R. A., Morris, J. G., Dunn, A., Boat, R., Dring, K. J., Nevill, M. E., & Cooper, S. B. (2025). Chronological age and biological maturity are separately positively associated with inhibitory control and working memory in boys and girls. *Frontiers in Cognition*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcogn.2025.1565625>

Gómez, D. L. J., Maestre, A. J. Á., Trujillo, A. E. P., Fuentes, C. a. P., Ortiz, D. H. B., & Alarcón, R. K. S. (2025). Determining factors for the development of critical thinking in higher education. *Journal of Intelligence*, 13(6), 59. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence13060059>

Guo, Y., & Lee, D. (2023). Leveraging ChatGPT for enhancing critical thinking skills. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 100(12), 4876–4883. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.3c00505>

Huang, J., Saleh, S., & Liu, Y. (2021). A review on artificial intelligence in education. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 10(3), 206. <https://doi.org/10.36941/ajis-2021-0077>

Jaswal, P., & Behera, B. (2023). Blended matters: Nurturing critical thinking. *E-Learning and Digital Media*, 21(2), 106–124. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20427530231156184>

Karakuş, İ. (2024). University students' cognitive flexibility and critical thinking dispositions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1420272>

Kim, B., Suh, H., Heo, J., & Choi, Y. (2020, September 18). *AI-Driven interface design for intelligent tutoring system improves student engagement*. arXiv.org. https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.08976?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Kung, T. H., Cheatham, M., Medenilla, A., Sillos, C., De Leon, L., Elepaño, C., Madriaga, M., Aggabao, R., Diaz-Candido, G., Maningo, J., & Tseng, V. (2023). Performance of ChatGPT on USMLE: Potential for AI-assisted medical education using large language models. *PLOS Digital Health*, 2(2), e0000198. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000198>

Lai, C. Y., Cheung, K. Y., & Chan, C. S. (2023). Exploring the role of intrinsic motivation in ChatGPT adoption to support active learning: An extension of the technology acceptance model. *Computers and Education Artificial Intelligence*, 5, 100178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2023.100178>

Lee, H., Chen, P., Wang, W., Huang, Y., & Wu, T. (2024). Empowering ChatGPT with guidance mechanism in blended learning: effect of self-regulated learning, higher-order thinking skills, and knowledge construction. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-024-00447-4>

Ngo, T. N., & Hastie, D. (2024). Artificial Intelligence for Academic Purposes (AIAP): Integrating AI literacy into an EAP module. *English for Specific Purposes*, 77, 20–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2024.09.001>

Statista. (2025, November 25). ChatGPT website traffic share 2024, by country. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1463911/chatgpt-chat-open-ai-com-traffic-share-by-country/>

- Susnjak, T. (2022). ChatGPT: The end of online exam integrity? *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2212.09292>
- Tan, X. (2023). The impact of ChatGPT on education and future prospects. *Highlights in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 61, 138–143. <https://doi.org/10.54097/hset.v61i.10285>
- Toplak, M. E. (2021). Foundations for the development of judgment and decision-making: Cognitive abilities, thinking dispositions, and specific knowledge. In *Elsevier eBooks* (pp. 23–52). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-816636-9.00001-3>
- Vázquez-Cano, E., Ramírez-Hurtado, J. M., Sáez-López, J. M., & López-Meneses, E. (2023). ChatGPT: The brightest student in the class. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 49, 101380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2023.101380>
- Wade, S., & Kidd, C. (2019). The role of prior knowledge and curiosity in learning. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 26(4), 1377–1387. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-019-01598-6>
- Wu, Y. (2024). Critical thinking pedagogics design in an era of ChatGPT and other AI tools — shifting from teaching “What” to teaching “Why” and “How.” *Journal of Education and Development*, 8(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.20849/jed.v8i1.1404>
- Yilmaz, H., Maxutov, S., Baitekoy, A., & Balta, N. (2023). Student attitudes towards Chat GPT: A technology acceptance model survey. *International Educational Review*, 1(1), 57–83. <https://doi.org/10.58693/ier.114>
- Zou, M., & Huang, L. (2023). To use or not to use? Understanding doctoral students’ acceptance of ChatGPT in writing through technology acceptance model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1259531>

